

YouCount
Youth Citizen Science

D1.1

Internet list of stakeholders (Revised)

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D1.1 Internet list of stakeholders

D1.1 Internet list of stakeholders to be part of a CSS network and established link to relevant CS projects [m4]

D1.1 stems from the work, that has been implemented under Work package (WP) 1 “Task 1.1. Identification and mobilising of stakeholders at the European and international levels”. This task is aimed at establishing a multilevel platform of stakeholders and seeks to link up the YouCount project to other CS-related projects and organizations.

This deliverable is public. As concerns the Horizon 2020 Work Programme types of deliverables, it is classified as: Demonstrator (DEM).

Table 1: Revision history

VERSION	DATE	CREATED BY	COMMENTS
1.0	03 / 05 / 2021	7, KTU	Draft structure and content of D.1.1 has been created and sent for comments
2.0	10 / 05 / 2021	7, KTU	Version incorporating comments from all consortium partners sent to SPOTTERON.
3.0	20 / 05 / 2021	7, KTU, 11, SPOTTERON	Online version of the Internet list of stakeholders finalized
4.0	28 / 05 / 2021	7, KTU	Version incorporating comments and suggestions by internal scientific reviewer.
5.0	31 / 05 / 2021	7, KTU, 1, OsloMet	Final version submitted
6.0	09 / 01 / 2023	7, KTU, 5, FD	Updated version for revision
7.0	25 / 01 / 2023	7, KTU, 1, OsloMet	Revised version submitted

Table 2: Terms and Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	FULL TERM
AB	Advisory Board
CoI	Community of Interest
CS	Citizen Science
CSS	Citizen Social Science
DEM	DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs. It is a type of deliverable. In this report we are referring to demonstrator as DEM.
EU	European Union
HEI	Higher Education Institution
RPO	Research Performing Organization
WP	Work Package
Y-CSS	Youth Citizen Social Science

Executive Summary

D1.1 presents the Internet list of stakeholders to be part of a CSS (citizen social science) network and established link to relevant CS (citizen science) projects and organizations.

D1.1 has been developed under WP1 Task 1.1. Identification and mobilising of stakeholders at the European and international levels. This task is aimed at establishing a multilevel platform of stakeholders and seeks to link up YouCount to other CS-related projects. In order to successfully develop co-creative CS, policy and innovation, the project partners started to identify, link up to and mobilise central experts and stakeholders at the European and national/local levels. D1.1 is the first milestone in the implementation of Task 1.1. This task is in progress and will be finished at the end of the project.

After the mid-term review of D1.1 on Month 18, the reviewer requested a revision of deliverable. The requested revision should add the list of current internet stakeholders. Thus, the revised version presents the updated version of the deliverable, describing the current situation and the further strategy of establishing a multilevel platform of stakeholders. In this revised version of the D1.1, we have expanded the understanding of CoI as an internet list to a broader list of stakeholders. The Internet list of stakeholders, first envisioned as online “community of interest” (further CoI) on YouCount website, is additionally expanded including also stakeholders that do not sign up for CoI on website, but are actively involved in YouCount activities, which makes them part of multilevel stakeholder platform. Thus, this deliverable is a living document that is constantly updated till Month 36 of the project implementation.

This deliverable is public. It consists of 2 parts: (1) The report (current document) and (2) The webpage “Community of Interest” on the YouCount website.

1. The development of the YouCount multilevel platform of stakeholders and online Col

The YouCount project aims to establish a multilevel platform where different stakeholders may express interest to be part of the YouCount community of interest. In YouCount project we understand multilevel platform of stakeholders as a broad network of stakeholders that are interested in YouCount activities and results and actively expressing this interest either by signing to online Col or engaging into other activities, organized by the project (follow up and interact on YouCount account on Twitter, participate actively in workshops, sign up for YouCount newsletter, etc.). This links up the YouCount project to other CS-related projects and organizations.

The development of the YouCount multilevel platform of stakeholders and establishment of Youcount community of interest is a lengthy process and D1.1 is the first important milestone in achieving this goal.

The process of the YouCount project multilevel platform of stakeholders and Col building to link up the YouCount to other CS-related projects and organizations has 3 major steps (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1: The process of the YouCount project multilevel platform of stakeholders and Col building

- **Establishing.** This step is focussed on creating the platform for YouCount project Col development. This includes creating of the webpage and online information submission form that is used on self-registered basis. The platform was opened for Col in April 2021.
- **Engaging and mobilizing.** This step aims at creating a list of potential stakeholders and inviting them to become part of YouCount project Col. Potential stakeholders were identified based on desk research and existing networks that consortium partners have. The invitations were disseminated on different levels: (1) European / international level: e.g. at Swafs programme projects at the monthly meetings, at ECSA webinars, other international and EU events, approaching international organizations, (2) national and local levels: relevant national projects, national institutions, local schools, youth organizations, community festivals, etc. The stakeholders were invited to register to Col by project consortium partners. This is ongoing process, and it will be finished at the end of the project implementation. Currently, the signing up for the online Col is still rather low and thus, the outreach to stakeholders via Col on website is limited. However, the interest in other YouCount activities (international webinars, local online and in-person events, ECSA WGs meetings, etc.) is high and the real outreach of stakeholders is definitely bigger than existing online Col.
- **Sustaining.** The creation and development of the YouCount community of interest is a lengthy process, thus the third step is aimed at engaging Col members for community activities, knowledge sharing webinars, learning practices, constant dissemination of project updates. This step started in 2023 and will run till the end of the project and beyond. Col will receive a monthly newsletter with updates about the project activities and results, be invited to webinars, seminars and other YouCount events such as conferences, also to co-creation workshops to find out the needs of different stakeholders and get their feedback, comments, suggestions for the project.

The timeline of multilevel platform of stakeholders and Col development is shown in Fig.2.

Figure 2: Timeline of multilevel platform of stakeholders and CoI development

2. Establishing the YouCount online community of interest

The Internet list of stakeholders (called on the webpage “community of interest”) is mobilising central stakeholders at the European and national/local levels. This will also help to engage stakeholders in dissemination and exploitation of project results.

The project collects information about stakeholders on self-registered basis. The stakeholders might be invited to register by project consortium partners (see Appendix A: An example / template of the invitation letter) or Advisory board (AB) members or do this on their own initiative.

The webpage provides an online information submission form. This form can be accessed on the same page: <https://www.youcountproject.eu/community-of-interest/add-your-organization> (see also Figure 3).

[Home](#)
[ABOUT](#)
[CONTACT](#)
[COMMUNITY OF INTEREST](#)

You are here: [Home](#) > [Community](#)

Add your organization to the community of interest

Figure 3 : Information submission option on the website

All submissions are reviewed by the responsible partner (KTU) to avoid incomplete submissions and the public information is displayed on the community of interest list.

Submission Form consists of public and non-public (private) information. Public information is displayed on website and non-public (private) information will be stored on MS Teams (password protected area) for direct contact only.

The following information is gathered about the stakeholders (see Table 3 and Figure 4):

Table 3: Information for submission form

Name of item	Public or private	Obligatory field	Notes
--------------	-------------------	------------------	-------

Stakeholder name	Public	Yes	Text input (please provide a full title and short acronym of the organization)
Description of the organization	Public	Yes	Text input (please provide a short, up to 100 words description of the organization and its activities. Please explicitly indicate the role(s) of the organizations (e.g. funding, educational, research, youth, etc.)
Type of stakeholder	Public	Yes	Choose from drop down menu: Governmental institution / Academia / Business organization / NGO or other CSO / Project / Local community / Youth organizations & centers / Youth media & influencers / Other
Category of stakeholder	Public	Yes	Choose from drop down menu: Global / EU level / National / Regional / Local / N/A
Website	Public	No	Text input
Organization email	Public	No	Text input
Address	Public	No	Text input
Country	Public	Yes	Choose from drop down menu: countries' list
Logo Upload (please as PNG in max. HD resolution)	Public	No	Option to upload
Contact person name/middlename (not public)	Non-public	Yes	Text input
Contact person surname (not public)	Non-public	Yes	Text input
Contact person position/role (not public)	Non-public	Yes	Text input
Contact person email (not public)	Non-public	Yes	Text input

Contact person phone number (not public)	Non-public	No	Text input
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Add your organization to the community of interest

Submission is reviewed by our team and the public information will be displayed on the community of interest list.

Submission Form

Public Information

The following information will be published on the website.

 Stakeholder Name ☆

 Description of organization ☆

Organization Type ☆

Organization Scope ☆

Figure 4: An example of the online submission form

3. Ethics relevance

Before submitting the form, all stakeholders are asked to read and confirm that they have read and understood the Terms of Use and Privacy Policy (see Figure 5).

Please read carefully the [Terms of Use](#) and [Privacy Policy](#) before proceeding with your registration. If you have any questions, please get in contact with website@yourcountproject.eu.

I have read and understood the [Terms of Use](#)

I have read and understood the [Privacy Policy](#)

Are you human? Please solve the Captcha:

SUBMIT

Figure 5: Online submission form: Terms of use and Privacy policy

3.1. Terms of Use (TOU)

GENERAL TERMS OF PARTICIPATION

You are registering for the community of interest database of the YouCount project.

By registering, you indicate your understanding and acceptance of these TOU and agree to be bound by them. Your access to registration is on condition of your acceptance of, and compliance with, these TOU. If you disagree with any part of the TOU then you should not register.

By agreeing, you express consent that the name and details of your organization will be shared on the YouCount website. Your personal contact details will not be publicly shared.

These TOU apply to all registering members of the community of interest.

CONDITIONS FOR REGISTRATION

Registration is voluntary.

Please be aware that if you decide to register, you may still unregister at any time without giving a reason. All information about you and your organization will then be deleted.

You also have the right to access your data and modify it.

To unregister or to modify your data, please send an e-mail to website@yourcountproject.eu specifying your request.

REASONS FOR PARTICIPATION

As the project is building an international network of organizations, working in this field, you may benefit from participation in its activities such as workshops, conferences and other project events, and explore opportunities for mutual learning, synergies and/or active collaboration.

PURPOSE OF THE PROJECT

YouCount - EMPOWERING YOUTH AND CO-CREATING SOCIAL INNOVATIONS AND POLICYMAKING THROUGH YOUTH-FOCUSED CITIZEN SOCIAL SCIENCE project (funded by EC programme H2020, Grant agreement ID: 101005931). Start date: 1 February 2021, End date: 31 January 2024.

YouCount aims to generate new knowledge and innovations to increase the social inclusion of youth at risk of exclusion across Europe through co-creative youth citizen social science. Youth (15 - 29 years) in nine European countries will participate as citizen scientists in case studies to explore positive drivers for social participation, employment, social belonging and citizenship.

The project will create a model for social inclusion and develop policy briefs and educational materials (with customized tools and best practices) for youth citizen social science (Y-CSS), and evaluation of citizen social science (CSS), to be used by researchers, individuals and citizen groups.

The project includes four sub-studies:

- 1) Development of a framework for Y-CSS together with a transdisciplinary consortium and multilevel platform of key experts and stakeholders in a European and international setting. The YouCount digital platform you are registering to is a part of this sub-study.
- 2) Implementation of a multiple case study of Y-CSS projects in nine countries across Europe where over 900 young citizen scientists and nine local living labs will co-create innovations together.
- 3) Mixed-methods evaluation of the outcomes and impact of the Y-CSS activities, and a multi-criteria assessment of the costs and benefits of Y-CSS, and
- 4) Creation of social and scientific impact through widespread scaling up and continuity. These activities will lead to robust knowledge and scientifically reasoned measures to promote Y-CSS and social change. The project will support dissemination and education in Y-CSS, and make synergies with other CSS related projects and initiatives, in particularly with citizen social science.

The project is coordinated by OSLOMET - STORBYUNIVERSITETET (Norway), and the Principal Investigator is Reidun Norvoll. The community of interest database of the YouCount project is curated by Kaunas University of Technology.

SAFETY & RISKS

There are no foreseeable risks involved in registering to this community of interest database. By providing information you grant permission for the data to be used for dissemination purposes related to implementation and promotion of the YouCount project.

CONTACT

If you have questions about the project or want to exercise your rights, contact:

Project Coordinator Reidun Norvoll at OsloMet via email: nore@oslomet.no.

OsloMet Data Protection Officer: Ingrid Jacobsen, by e-mail: ingrid.jacobsen@oslomet.no, or by telephone; + 47 993 02 316

NSD – The Norwegian Centre for Research Data AS, by email: personverntjenester@nsd.no, or by telephone: +47 55 58 21 17.

3.2. Privacy policy

Data Privacy Policy: Informed consent used for online registration

You are registering to the community of interest database of the YouCount project.

The name and details of your organization will be shared on the YouCount website. Your personal contact details will not be shared publicly.

PURPOSE OF THE PROJECT

YouCount - EMPOWERING YOUTH AND COCREATING SOCIAL INNOVATIONS AND POLICYMAKING THROUGH YOUTH-FOCUSED CITIZEN SOCIAL SCIENCE project (funded by EC programme H2020, Grant agreement ID: 101005931). Start date: 1 February 2021, End date: 31 January 2024.

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years) in nine European countries will participate as citizen scientists in case studies to explore positive drivers for social participation, employment, social belonging and citizenship.

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2) Implementation of a multiple case study of Y-CSS projects in nine countries across Europe where over 900 young citizen scientists and nine local living labs will co-create innovations together.

3) Mixed-methods evaluation of the outcomes and impact of the Y-CSS activities, and a multi-criteria assessment of the costs and benefits of Y-CSS, and

4) Creation of social and scientific impact through widespread scaling up and continuity. These activities will lead to robust knowledge and scientifically reasoned measures to promote Y-CSS and social change. The project will support dissemination and education in Y-CSS, and make synergies with other CSS related projects and initiatives, in particularly with citizen social science.

The project is coordinated by OSLOMET - STORBYUNIVERSITETET (Norway), and the Principal Investigator is Reidun Norvoll. The community of interest database of YouCount project is curated by Kaunas University of Technology.

DATA STORAGE

Submitted data is processed and stored by Spotteron GmbH as a processor and on server by Host Europe GmbH as a sub-processor.

During the project implementation, the collected data will also be stored in MS Teams. At the end of the project, your data will be kept until 31 January, 2028 and will then be destroyed.

CONFIDENTIALITY

The name and details of your organization will be shared openly on the YouCount website. Please do not provide any information that you do not wish to be shared openly on the website. Your personal contact details will not be shared publicly.

The data provided by you will not be transferred to any third party nor processed in a manner inconsistent with the purposes for which it has been initially collected. In case of the continuation

of the digital platform after the completion of the project, you will be asked to provide a new consent.

YOUR RIGHTS

You have the right to:

- access the data that is being processed about you and your organization
- request that your data is deleted
- request that incorrect data is corrected/rectified
- send a complaint to:

Project Coordinator Reidun Norvoll at OsloMet via email: nore@oslomet.no.

OsloMet Data Protection Officer: Ingrid Jacobsen, by e-mail: ingrid.jacobsen@oslomet.no, or by telephone; + 47 993 02 316

NSD – The Norwegian Centre for Research Data AS, by email: personverntjenester@nsd.no, or by telephone: +47 55 58 21 17.

COOKIE POLICY

The website is respecting your digital privacy and includes no external analytics software nor scripts of third parties. The website is just processing session cookies for user authorization.

LOG FILES

Your IP address, date, access and origin are stored in standard server log files and are not shared externally.

DATA CONTROLLER

Data controller is project coordinator OsloMet – storbyuniversitetet (Postboks 4, St. Olavs plass, 0130 Oslo).

DATA PROCESSOR

Contracted as the data processor is Spotteron GmbH. Submitted data is processed and stored by Spotteron GmbH (Faßziehergasse 5 - AT 1070 Vienna).

SUB-PROCESSORS

The website is hosted on a server by Host Europe GmbH (Hansestrasse 111, 51149 Köln, Register number: HRB 28495) as a sub-processor of all website related data.

LEGAL BASIS

The lawful procession for a) invitation to be registered on the list is based on GDPR art. 6 no. 1f Legitimate interest and b) publishing and use of the data on the homepage and the YouCount MS Teams platform is based on GDPR art. 6. nr. 1 Informed consent.

CONTACT

If you have questions about the project, or want to exercise your rights, contact:

Project Coordinator Reidun Norvoll at OsloMet via email: nore@oslomet.no.

OsloMet Data Protection Officer: Ingrid Jacobsen, by e-mail: ingrid.jacobsen@oslomet.no, or by telephone; + 47 993 02 316

NSD – The Norwegian Centre for Research Data AS, by email: personverntjenester@nsd.no, or by telephone: +47 55 58 21 17.

4. The internet list of community of interest (Col)

The current list of Col members consists of 15 members (see Table 4). This list will be continuously updated to ensure an appropriate impact after the project has ended.

The full internet list of stakeholders (Col) is accessible through the link on YouCount webpage: <https://www.youcountproject.eu/community-of-interest>

Table 4: Community of Interest: Internet list of stakeholders

Name of organization	Type	Scope	Country
Institute for Global Prosperity, UCL	Academia	Global	United Kingdom
UP Medical School Institute of Transdisciplinary Discoveries	Academia	Global	Hungary
University of Central Lancashire	Academia	Global	United Kingdom
La Comarca Científica	Academia	Global	Hungary
Orkestra-Basque Institute of Competitiveness	Academia	EU level	Spain
Hungarian Permaculture Association	NGO or other CSO	National	Hungary

Citizen Science as an Innovative Form of Citizen Participation for Welfare society	Other (project)	National	Lithuania
Work Research Institute (AFI)	Academia	National	Norway
Lithuanian Citizen Science Association	NGO or other CSO	National	Lithuania
Oslo Metropolitan University (OsloMet)	Academia	National	Norway
ELTE Department of Media and Communication	Academia	National	Hungary
Die Wiener Volkshochschulen GmbH (Wiener VHS)	Other	Regional	Austria
JU:MP	NGO or other CSO	Local	United Kingdom
Humanitarian Enhancement Aid for Resilient Transformation-	NGO or other CSO	Local	Bangladesh
Tøyen Unlimited	NGO or other CSO	Local	Norway

5. The potential stakeholder groups for further outreach

As planned, YouCount project establishes multilevel platform of experts and stakeholders, develops links to exchange experiences and create synergies with relevant CS projects and initiatives as well as with youth organisations on all levels (e.g., youth councils/forums).

The multilevel platform of stakeholders is developed including 5 major levels:

- global (stakeholders operating on global level)
- EU (stakeholders operating on EU level)

- National (stakeholders operating on particular country level)
- Regional (stakeholders operating on particular region within a country level)
- Local (stakeholders operating on local level, which includes city, town, township, neighbourhood, etc.)

Stakeholders include all 4 types of organizations of Quadruple Helix: (1) Academia, (2) Businesses, (3) Government and (4) NGOs and other CSOs, as well as active citizens.

The YouCount project aims to make outreach of the particular groups as potential stakeholders (see Table 5). In YouCount WP1 (Task 1.1. Identification and mobilising of stakeholders at the European and international levels) works closely and in symbiosis with WP5, in which the active outreach activities are organized. The outreach activities, performed under WP5, target organizations and individuals.

Multilevel platform of experts and stakeholders is understood as mobilization of individuals and organizations as an active subjects interested in the YouCount project idea and results. Some of these stakeholders are mobilized into online Col (voluntarily signing on the YouCount website, Col members are just organizations), however, others (especially individuals) are mobilized through different activities performed by the YouCount project: workshops, webinars, conferences, dissemination events, webinars, ECSA and ECSA WGs events, etc. YouCount considers them as an extended informal Col, relevant for the project goals.

Table 5. List of Stakeholder Groups and Stakeholders identified by YouCount project for outreach and creation of multilevel platform

Stakeholder group	Explanation (examples)
Academic Institution, HEIs	YouCount targets to reach Universities, Colleges, Research Institutes and other RPOs within and outside EU (on organization level)
Academic community	YouCount targets to reach teachers, students, researchers, management of HEIs or RPOs (on individual level).

Stakeholder group	Explanation (examples)
CS organizations and practitioners	YouCount targets people and organizations that have experience in initiating, developing, and implementing CS projects (on organization and individual level)
Science communication organisations	YouCount targets organizations that primarily or indirectly perform science communication functions (on organization level)
Relevant EU Institutions and policy makers as well as officials on EU level (and science policy makers in particular)	YouCount targets EU institutions and individual policy makers and officials that are potentially interested in project topic and activities (on organization and individual level). F.e.: officials from European Commission, policy makers from EU parliament, etc. (on organization and individual level)
Relevant policy making and governmental institutions and policy makers as well as officials on national level (and science policy makers in particular)	YouCount targets national policy making and governmental institutions and individual policy makers and officials that are potentially interested in project topic and activities (on organization and individual level). F.e.: national parliament, ministries, etc. (on organization and individual level)
Relevant governmental institutions and policy makers as well as officials on local level	YouCount targets local governmental institutions and individual policy makers and officials that are potentially interested in project topic and activities (on organization and individual level). F.e.: municipalities, local governments, etc. (on organization and individual level)
Science funding organizations	YouCount targets research funding organizations (national and international). F.e. national Research Councils, national and international research foundations (on organization level)
Schools	YouCount targets schools and school communities (administration, teachers, schoolchildren, their parents) from different countries (in particular, project partner countries) (on organization and individual level)
Youth organizations	YouCount targets youth organizations and activists on international, national, regional, and local level (on organization and individual level)
NGOs related to social inclusion, social innovations, CS and other relevant for YouCount topics	YouCount targets non-governmental organizations and activists on international, national, regional, and local level (on organization and individual level)

Stakeholder group	Explanation (examples)
Local communities	YouCount targets communities on local level (on community level)
Community planners and entrepreneurs/cooperatives	YouCount targets community activists, planners, entrepreneurs from local settings (on organization and individual level)
SMEs and other businesses	YouCount targets SMEs, other business companies, especially social businesses and social enterprises (on organization and individual level)
General public, and young people in particular	YouCount engages general public that are interested in project activities and results (on individual level)
Advisory Board	YouCount engages Advisory Board members (on individual level)
ECSA and other international and national CS associations	YouCount targets ECSA and other international and national CS associations

In building multilevel stakeholder platform, the particular attention is paid to developing links, exchanging experiences and creating synergies with relevant CS projects and initiatives. Potentially the YouCount project identified projects (currently running or already successfully finished, in particular, CS projects in the SwafS call), other R&I initiatives, existing European infrastructures that are relevant for YouCount project activities. Some of identified projects and initiatives are presented in Appendix B.

Appendixes

Table 6: Appendixes

APPENDIX	SUBJECT	PAGE
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Appendix A. An example / template of invitation letter

Dear [name of the invited person],

You are invited to join a community of interest in the youth citizen social science topic, under the project YouCount - Empowering Youth and Cocreating Social Innovations and Policymaking through Youth-Focused Citizen Social Science funded by EC programme H2020 (Grant agreement ID: 101005931).

This project is led by Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway. YouCount aims to generate new knowledge and innovations to increase the social inclusion of youth at risk of exclusion across Europe through co-creative youth citizen social science. The project will create a model for social inclusion and develop policy briefs and educational materials with customised tools and best practices for youth citizen social science and evaluation of citizen social science to be used by researchers, individuals and citizen groups. You may read more about the project in: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101005931>

YouCount also seeks to establish a network of academic, business, and non-governmental and government organizations working in the field of youth social inclusion, social innovations and citizen science.

With this letter, we would like to invite you to join this community, to be informed about the events and results of the project, and, most importantly, to explore opportunities for mutual learning, synergies and/or active collaboration.

When registering you will have to agree with Data privacy policy and Terms of use which are provided at the registration site [link will direct to registration web form].

If you would like to register, please use this link [link will direct to registration web form].

Kind regards,

[name of the inviting person]

Appendix B. List of projects and initiatives targeted by YouCount project for multilevel stakeholder platform (examples)

Projects and initiatives	Level/notes
European Youth Forum	International, European level
European Academy of Youth Work (www.eayw.net)	European level
CoE-EC Youth Partnership	International, 50 signatory states of the European Cultural Convention
ARCS – ARenas for Cooperation through Citizen Science	Sweden
African youth enterprise organisation YALDA	Outside EU
ECS, http://eu-citizen.science/ (Previous: EU-Citizen. Science)	EU funded project
AURORA, https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/	EU funded project
CoAct, https://coactproject.eu/	EU funded project
Cities-Health, http://citieshealth.eu/	EU funded project
COESO, https://coeso.hypotheses.org/	EU funded project
COMPAIR, https://www.wecompair.eu	EU funded project
Crowd4SDG, https://crowd4sdg.eu/	EU funded project
CS Track, https://cstrack.eu/	EU funded project
CSI-COP, https://csi-cop.eu/	EU funded project
Envirocitizen, https://www.envirocitizen.eu/	EU funded project
FRANCIS, https://www.francis-project.eu/	EU funded project
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STEP-CHANGE, https://stepchangeproject.eu/	EU funded project
TIME4CS, https://www.time4cs.eu/	EU funded project

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